

The Sitala Culture and Social System: A Study on Socio-cultural Change in Midnapore District in Bengal (19th to 21st Centuries)

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Abstract

Devi Sitala is known as 'queen of diseases' in India, and regarding her, different types of legends are popular over the India as well as Bengal. In Midnapore district Devi Sitala become as a compulsory village deity for protection from various diseases. With the appearance of various fatal diseases like cholera, small-pox, malaria, Burdwan fever etc. in Midnapore district in nineteenth century, the worship of Devi Sitala started to famous in village to village. According to legendary source of Midnapore, there were sixty-four types of poxes and Sitala was the provider. A culture is found regarding the Sitala devi and the customs are following by the native people. Customs of worship, prohibition to take non-veg, neem tika for affected small-pox patients, different types of Sitala pala gan, compulsory establishment of Sitala temple at village premises etc. It is a kind compulsion to worship Sitala before starting any auspicious ceremony at home. The British Government took several steps against the small-pox and vaccination done to lakhs people in Midnapore district in every year, people realized that it's a caused by infection with the variola virus, but till the present time the Sitala culture much popular in both districts of Midnapore. In this culture different medicinal plants are used for pox and other diseases. The present study will find out the condition of Sitala culture in 21st century and why people are involved in Sitala culture and what is the scientific reason behind it where being highest educated district (East Midnapore) of West Bengal. Moreover, the relationship between Sitala and the diseases, health condition, various dimensions of Sitala culture etc. are highlighted in the paper.

Keywords

Sitala Culture, Small-pox, Health, Sitala Pala Gan, Vaccine, Native Medicines.

Introduction

With the passing of time, society is being changed. In undivided Midnapore district of West Bengal in India, a new cultural system is flourishing with popular deity Sitala. Among the Hindus, social system, nobody could ignore the Devi Sitala, who is involved in everyday life rituals. In this modern society, Goddess Sitala's popularity has not wanted in the slightest. Although Devi Sitala was originated as the protector from diseases or 'Queen of diseases and the passing of time its impact fall on various grounds, like religion, ceremonies, wedding, housewarming, and any other auspicious occasion. The study highlights the Sitala-centered social system in Midnapore. In Midnapore, Devi Sitala is also known as *Nachinda Ma*, *Bhaitamari Ma*, *Buri Ma*, *Baro Ma* etc.

Objective of study

All above writers have not mentioned on Midnapore district and its fatality of small pox. Beside it, in Midnapore a new socio-cultural system has been found with the deity Sitala. Sitala is not involved only on small-pox or other diseases, its impact fall on entire Hindu socio-cultural system over the Midnapore (present-Purba Medinipur, Paschim Medinipur). How the Goddess Sitala transformed from Goddess of disease into the Goddess of fortune. The study will seek out Sitala centric new culture and its various charges in 20th and 21st century Midnapore.

Review of Literature

Regarding Sitala and small pox, a few researches have been done, David Arnold in his 'New Cambridge History of India Science Technology and Medicine in Colonial India' pointed out about fatality of small pox and people started to worship Devi Sitala. Wadley S. Susan wrote in his book 'Sitala: The cool one' (1980) companies on Sitala worship its spread over India. He has focused on the small-pox and its connection with Sitala. Sitala was treated as queen of diseases. Different District Gazetteers and Census Reports at also mentioned dangerous condition of smallpox.

Methodology

To prepare this study I have followed a qualitative research methodology. Data have been collected from various primary sources and secondary sources. Like Census reports, Gazetteers, statistical accounts, book, newspaper, journals, finally took interviews of different prominent persons who are involved with Sitala culture. Then shorted the data and unnecessary data are

removed. After that the valuable data arranged in systematic way and finally took decision and the sturdy is prepared.

Introducing Midnapore District:

Undivided Midnapore district was the largest and most important district of West Bengal. Midnapore district has been divided into two parts East Midnapore and Paschim Midnapore districts on 1st January 2002. The district was located from 2136' to 2257' north latitude and 8633' to 8811' longitude.¹ A number of rivers flow over the Midnapore district. The rivers influenced occupation, economy, food, and health condition of the people. In addition, through the rivers and jungles various types of diseases appeared in Midnapore district through the ages, and several types of medicinal plants grow up besides the river banks. These rivers are-Hooghly River, Haldi River, Rupnarayan river, Rasulpur River, Subarnarakha River etc.²

In 1793 during the time of Permanent Settlement, the 6 jungle mahals of Burdwan division were transformed to this Midnapore district for administrative convenience. In 1809, the first Revenue Collector was appointed for Birbhum and Midnapore, and an administrative building for the Magistrate was built at Bankura.³ From 1815-1829, a Joint Magistrate was appointed to work independently in Midnapore. In 1929, the first full-fledged magistrate was appointed for the district.⁴ According to the first census report, the population of Midnapore district was 2,542,920 (in 1872), but in the second census report, the population of Midnapore district was decreased and stand to 2,515,565. According to O' Malley, the rising fever epidemic throughout South Bengal in the 1870 was so severe that the population of Midnapore declined by 250,000.⁵ The population of East Midnapore in 2011 is 5,095,875. Among these 2,629,834 are males and 2,466,061 are female.⁶ One the other hand, in 2011, the population of West Midnapore is 5,913,457, and 3,007,885 males and 2,905,572 are female.⁷

Origin of Sitala Culture in Midnapore:

According to legendary source of Midnapore, Devi Sitala is known as the 'mother of diseases' (*bedhi janani*). Devi Sitala is a daughter of Bramha.⁸ The name of her husband is Ghantakarna. She also worships by different communities of North India, West Bengal, Nepal, Bangladesh, and Pakistan. In Gurgaon, Devi Sitala is known as the wife of Dronacharya. In some place she is known as 'Sital' (cool) also. Not only that, she is worshipped by Muslim also as 'Burabubu'. By Buddhist as she is worshiped as 'Harit', 'Mari Amma' to South India and 'Usha' to Chinese.⁹ In Midnapore she is known as Sitala Mata, Brahmeshwari, Bedhi janani, Karunamayee, Marsumi Devi, Thakurani, Dayamayee, Bhagabati, Mangala etc. The following chant is popular in Midnapore. ¹⁰

<u>Bengali</u>	<u>English</u>
শিতলাঃ গর্ধবাঃ রুডায়	Sitala mounted an ass
শ্যাম বর্ণাঃ সুলচনাঃ	She is black by colour
দক্ষিণে মার জরিমুঠান	A broom in her right hand
বামে কলস ধারিনী	A pot with full of water in her left hand
দিগম্বরী হাসানমুখি	A winnowing fan is backside of her head
সুরপালংকিত মন্ডকাঃ	Digambari mother Sitala is always smiley.

From February to June (*Phalgun, Chaitra, Baishakh, Jaisthya*) are fixed to celebrate the *Sitala pala gan*.¹¹ The worship of Sitala in Bengal rarely occurs on a fixed *tithi* (date). Although the Bengali almanacs list *Phalgun Krishnastami* as the proper day for Sitala worship, only a few household pujas are held on this day. ¹²

There are various opinions about the origin of Sitala. The Goddess Sitala originated from the combat of the yajna of Nahus king. After the arrival in earth of the Goddess Sitala, she appealed for his worship to the country-men. But nobody accepts her appeal. She became anger by the attitude of the earth dwellers. Then she spread sixty-four types of poxes to the different type of cast and communities to make a fear and panic among the country-men. Being feared the people started to worship of Sitala, after that she was known as Devi Sitala. People also offered *palagan* (periodical song) to Sitala for making impress her. Which is fatal over the Midnapore district. With the increase of small-pox in Bengal the rituals of worship of Sitala also

popularizes day by day. It was noticed that places where the small pox were fatal character and people started to establish Sitala temple in their villages.

There is a fundamental relation in between Devi Sitala and the small-pox which is emphasized in the Sitala Mangal. According to the different manuscripts¹³ of Sitala *palagan* and legendary stories Sitala is associated with Jarasur, the Fever Demon, and Raktabati (she who possesses the Blood), both her servant demon and they are a form of pox. With these two aids, Sitala spreads her poxes, though the medium of lentils (Amar Kalai), among those who refuse to worship her.¹⁴ Comparatively we can say that in Manasa Mangal, Manasa associated with the *kalnag* (snake) to get worship the country-men. Similarly, Sitala also associated the Jarasur and Raktabati to spread different types of poxes and other disease to get worship from the country-men including the kings of the country. When Manasa depressed regarding her worship, she ordered to bite *kalnag* (snake) to eight sons of Chand Sadagar and resulted they were death. Similar Sitala also spread the small-pox to the sons of Virat king and they were death. At least Chand Sadagar admitted to worship the Devi Manasa and similarly king Virat started to worship Devi Sitala. In this way Sitala worship was introduced in this earth.¹⁵ Ancient text also said these same talks, like Hindu puran, Skanda puran, Manasa Mangal, Brahmabrata. According to Purana, at that time one asur (demon) name Jarasur was spread incurable diseases, all over the world, cholera, measles and small pox were scattered. No hakim and kabiraj could not cured these diseases. Then Devi Parvati descended to the earth as the daughter of Sage Katyan. Her father named her Katyani. Katyani started curing the diseases from the childhood. One day, Jarasur can knows the truth and get angry and increase the disease. Then katayani request Shiva to fight the Jarasur and defeat him. Lord Shiva deseeded to the earth young man named Batuk. After that, a war between Batuk and Jarasur was started. Batuk heats the Jarasur by a Trident (Trisul) than Jarasur become Senseless. later Katayani was known as Sitale and rescue the people from different type of diseases.¹⁶ With the passing of time the character of Sitala worship has been transformed. Once Sitala worshipped to rescue from the diseases but in recent times the deity is worship for *Dharma* (religion), *Artho* (wealth), *Kam* (sex), *Mokkha* (Nirvana).¹⁷

Small-pox and the Sitala worship in 19th and 20th Centuries:

O' Malley has explained various types of diseases in 'Bengal District Gazetteers' in 19th centuries Bengal. These were malarial fever, small-pox, cholera, hepatitis and spleen, elephantiasis leprosy etc. He also mentioned many viral fevers. These were Bilious remittent fever, Typhoid fever, Thermion fever, cerebrospinal fever, Influenza, Inflammatory and Elephantoid fever.¹⁸

The Midnapore district suffered severely from the epidemic fever known as Burdwan fever. This fever made its appearance in the north of this district 1871. Next Year a great southern through the whole of the alluvial counter of the district. The third year the epidemic was at its worst, the mortality being twice great as in the preceding year. but in 1874 it was less fatal and less prevalent. In 1875 the same facts were observed again. The total mortality caused by the epidemic in Midnapore during the year in which it regard was estimated at 250,000.¹⁹

In 1873-1874, 500,000 people died from Small-pox in India.²⁰ The mortality from Small pox is as a rule inconsiderable but occasional epidemic break out. The worst on record occurred in 1902 and caused 17,841 deaths, representing a mortality of no less than 6.39 per mile in Midnapore.²¹ Over 15,000 people died from small-pox between January and May 1974. Most of the deaths occurred in the Indian states of Bihar, Odisha and West Bengal. There are thousands who survived but were disfigured or blinded. India reported 61,482 cases of small-pox to World Health Organization (WHO) in these five months. India had over 86% of the world's small pox cases in 1974, primarily due to this epidemic.²² The pantheon of Hindu deities reflects a variety of divine attributes, and smallpox is traditionally regarded as the manifestation of one of the deities, the goddess Shitala, or Shitala-Ma, whose name means "the cool one," or "cooling mother" (Maury 1969). In southern India her name is Mariamma (Mather and John 1973); in Maharashtra it is Mata-May (Junghare 1975); in rural Bihar she is Bhagwathi (Hassan 1975); in Madhya Pradesh she is Maharani; and in areas of eastern India, she is Ai (O.P. Jaggi 1973). Other names for her include Devi Mata, Maha-Mai, and Jag Rani (Crooke 1968). In conventional Hindu theology, Shitala is one of seven (sometimes nine) sisters (sometimes mothers), each of whom is associated with a different disease. These diseases commonly include chicken-pox, measles, mumps, and cholera.²³ The worship of Shitala sometimes

conflicted with acceptance of smallpox vaccination, since some Hindus felt that vaccination would anger the Goddess.

Smallpox is attributed to the wrath of the Goddess, which is especially likely to occur should rituals in her honour be neglected. A popular Hindi poem to Sitala says, “*when the body burns with poisonous eruptions, you make it cool and take away all pain*” (Prabhudas edited, 1977). The most common traditional prophylaxis for the disease was regular fulfillment of spiritual obligations to Sitala. Religious ceremonies were periodically performed in her honour at temples dedicated to her throughout the country, in the village environs, or in the home.²⁴ David Arnold has explained from a mere 350,000 vaccinations in British India in 1850, the number rose to 4.5 million in 1877, by which time there were more than 2,500 full-time vaccinators. By the 1890s the annual number of vaccinations had risen to nearly 8 million and by early in the twentieth century to 9 million.²⁵

Situation of Sitala Culture in 21st Century in Midnapore:

Regarding Sitala Devi, a culture is popular in Midnapore. Now a days Devi Sitala become as compulsory village deity as the chief protector. The worship of Sitala is mandatory before any other auspicious occasion at home like Marriage, *Annoprason* (first feeding of solid food), *Griha Prabesh* (entrance the new house), inauguration of new business, birth day celebration and other activities. Regarding her blessing people promised *Manat* (Swear to Devi), Sitala *Pala gan* is offer her in every village. There are eight types of Sitala *Pala gan*. These are Nimai Jagatir Pala, Paravromon Pala, Maddhom Virat, Himghat, Basantabitaran Pala, Lanka Puja, Chandi Mangal, Srimanta Mosan.²⁶

At the present time Devi Sitala is much popular to the people in Midnapore and no body dare to ignore her. Regarding different activities a new culture is noticed among the people and a social system is originated which is called ‘Sitala Culture.’ Many say, small-pox is mother’s (Sitala) kindness. Although there is scientific treatment system is available for small pox but people are worshiping Sitala to get relief from it beside the treatment. In the Sitala culture there are many rituals for affected small pox people, for example- prohibition on taking non-veg, puffed rice (*muri*), boiling paddy, cutting on nail and hair etc. Moreover, pox affected patient received *Nim tika* (a paste made by neem leaf and turmeric must be message on hole body) from the Sitala temple. Advise to taken juice of ginger, honey, water of green coconut and other easy digestive foods. In addition, Kalmegh for fever symptom, *muri jol* for vomiting, garlic for headache symptom etc. herbal medicines are used. After fifteen days, the worship of Sitala at temple premises with offering *prasad* is compulsory rituals.²⁷ The people of Midnapore cannot think any more without before Sitala Devi and she is a part of livelihood of the people. Even the scientists of ISRO prayed and worshiped to Tirupati temple before launch the Chandrayaan III and got success, similarly people of Midnapore being higher educated prays and worships of Devi Sitala. And one ISRO scientist name Pijus Kanti Pattanayek belongs of Midnapore took part in Chandrayaan Mission III believed on Devi Sitala. It may be said that the modern and logical society of Midnapore accepted heartily Sitala culture as their daily life.

Conclusion

The study finds out the situation of Midnapore district in 19th and 20th Century, origin of Sitala culture and its extension of popularity and progress, Sitala how became optional (requirement) to compulsory village Goddess, protector from disease to all welfare of society. People remember the Goddess dawn to dust and from birth to death. In Midnapore, people don’t think that without Sitala cannot be lived. Entire social system has been changed with Sitala, fear and loves both are made a new social order, which is Sitala culture. It is not possible to present the entire scope of such a large-scale research topic in a single article. A great deal of research should be done in this topic, and then many issues in society can be highlighted.

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